

Determining Parameters for Wood Attenuation Coefficient Estimation

Elijah E. Onwoke¹, Timothy C. Akpa² and Taofeeq A. Ige³

¹Department of Medical Physics, Federal University of Health Sciences, Otuokpo, Nigeria.

²Nigerian Nuclear Regulatory Agency, Abuja, Nigeria.

³Department of Radiology, National Hospital, Abuja, Nigeria.

Received 12 June 2024; Acceptance 24 June 2024; Published 27 June 2024.

Abstract

Medical radiation shielding assessment is made possible by accurate estimation of attenuation coefficient of shielding materials employed. This research aims to determine the parameters which correctly estimate the attenuation of woods which are non-hazardous and readily afford as shielding materials. In this study, a total of five types of woods, namely, African Balsam, Gmelina, Tectona Grandis, Ironwood and Mahogany were collected from Agan forest located along Makurdi-Lafia Road, Makurdi, north central Nigeria. The wood samples were oven-dried with temperature range of 90 - 120 to remove water and the attenuation coefficient determining parameters estimated. Results in this finding indicate that wood quality can be based on the gamma ray attenuation characteristics for which Mahogany recorded the highest value of 0.4158cm^{-1} and 1.6518cm^{-1} , and followed by sampled Iron Wood which has a value of 0.4084cm^{-1} and 1.6354cm^{-1} respectively. The linear attenuation coefficient of the wood species in this research was found to depend on the energy of incident photons, the density and nature of the wood species. Mahogany with average density of 0.776g/cm^3 has the highest attenuation coefficient while African Balsam with average density of 0.43g/cm^3 has the lowest attenuation coefficient.

Keywords: Radiation, Wood Attenuation, and Density.

Introduction

Studies on interaction of gamma radiation have been the subject of interest for many decades. The study of gamma-rays interaction with materials of common and industrial use, as well as of biological and commercial importance has made great impact in the fields of atomic physics, agriculture, cancer therapy, environmental science, forensic science, health physics, materials science and radiation physics [1]. For a scientific study of interaction of radiation with matter, a proper characterization and assessment of penetration and diffusion of gamma rays in the external medium is necessary. We can define some

Correspondence to: Elijah Onwoke, e-mail: ebibi.onwoke@fuhso.edu.ng

Copyright: © 2024 The authors. This is an Open Access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License.

How to Cite: Onwoke et al. (2024). Determining Parameter for Wood Attenuation Coefficient Estimation. *Annals of Environment*, **1(6)**. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12548275

parameters such as quantitative evaluation, of which 'the mass attenuation coefficient' of the material is one of the most important parameters. It is because of this that the study of mass attenuation coefficient of various materials has been an important part of research work in radiation chemistry and physics. The mass attenuation coefficient usually depends upon the energy of radiation and nature of the material such as concrete, lead, water and cellulose (wood) [2].

On the other hand, a shielding material is expected to have high gamma ray attenuation coefficient in order that a small thickness will produce significant reduction in gamma radiation intensity. The practice, for example, is to use lead (Pb) lining on doors of X-rays room. However, the observation is that a large number of X-rays facilities use wooden door of different thickness without lead lining. A number of researches [3], [4] have shown that wood sample of average thickness could be used to offer radiation shielding. In [5], the properties of wood were evaluated alongside their natural abilities in shielding hazardous radiation with a view to documenting their shielding potentials. [6] examined the attenuation of diagnostic X-rays (at 60kVp) by the wood of six wood species in Nigeria, and observed a relative mean adsorption of between 0.951cm and 0.967cm at the maximum wood thickness of 10cm. The study was intended to elucidate the wood structure of these hardwood species with a view to providing possible explanations for the anatomical basis of their X-ray shielding abilities.

According to [7], the density of wood, exclusive of water, varies greatly both within and between species. Although the density of most species falls between about 320 and 720 g/cm³ the range of density actually extends from about 160 g/cm³ for balsa to more than 1,040 g/cm³ for some other imported woods. A coefficient of variation of about 10% is considered suitable for describing the variability of density within common domestic species. To this end, this research aims to determine the parameters which correctly estimate the attenuation of woods which are non-hazardous and readily afford as shielding materials.

Materials and method

Sample collection

Five types of woods for this research work were collected from Agan forest. The wood samples were identified with their common names and include African Balsam (AB), Gmelina (GA), Mahogany (MH), Ironwood (IW) and Teak (TG).

Sample analysis

The samples were oven-dried with temperature range from 90 – 120 °C. Samples were also weighed until constant weights were obtained which showed that the water was completely removed. The dried wood samples were further treated by soaking in water for twenty-one days to determine the effects of gamma radiation on wet wood and they were irradiated.

Physical dimensions of the wood

The samples were cut into a dimension such that the structural shielding can fit into the sample holder which it was rectangular form and was designed to maintain constant geometry during each counting operations. The sample was kept in between the source and the detector at 4cm distance interval. The volume of the samples for block or slice was determined by multiplying their length breadth (Area) thickness. For each sample, length, breadth and thickness were measured separately.

Estimation Method

The attenuation determining parameters of the aforementioned wood samples were estimated using a combination of analytical and semi-empirical methods. The values obtained for the wood samples are a means to estimate the attenuation coefficient of each wood.

Attenuation determining parameters

Determination of sample wood thickness

The thickness of each wood sample was determined using Vernier Caliper, an instrument that incorporates the Vernier scale, a main scale and a fixed sliding jaw. It gives a direct reading of the distance between two opposite sides of an object and high precision measurement.

Determination of wood density

The density of each wood sample was determined using equation (1)

$$\rho = \frac{m}{v} \quad (1)$$

Where ρ is the density, v is volume, and m is the mass of the wood sample.

Variation of incident radiation with wood sample

A background radiation was established by counting radiation beam intensity of the surrounding radiation, while the shutter of the source holder is closed. In order to avoid irregularities in the counts of the background radiation due to gas amplification in the counter, the counting was done several times before and after the experiment. The time for the counting was set for 900second which considered standard in determining the intensities of gamma –rays. The radiation counter was set at 820 Volt which is considered as a standard value and a collimated beam was allowed to pass through the samples from which the attenuated beam intensity was measured using Geiger Mueller Detector. For each thickness, series of counts were recorded from a detector to obtain the average count. The attenuation coefficient has been measured comparing the attenuated intensity and the unattenuated intensity, which are the measured count rates, with and without the absorber using the Beer-Lambert's formula [8]:

$$I = I_0 e^{-\mu x} \quad (2)$$

Where I_0 is the number of counts recorded in the detector before attenuation, I is the number of counts recorded in the detector attenuation, μ is the linear attenuation coefficient (cm^{-1}) and x is the thickness of the wood samples in cm. Taking natural logarithm of equation (2), we obtain:

$$\mu x = \ln \frac{I_0}{I} \quad (3)$$

Solving equation (3) for μ , we get:

$$\mu = \frac{1}{x} \ln \frac{I_0}{I} \quad (4)$$

Results and Discussion

Table1: Physical dimensions of sampled wood

	Sample A	Sample B	Sample C	Sample D	Sample E	Sample F
Thickness (Cm)	0.4	0.8	1.2	1.6	2.0	2.4
Area (Cm ²)	46.24	46.24	46.24	46.24	46.24	46.24
Volume (Cm ³)	18.50	36.99	55.49	73.98	92.48	110.98

Figure 1: a plot of $\ln(I_0/I)$ against thickness x for African Balsam at (1173-1332 KeV)

Figure 2: a plot of $\ln(I_0/I)$ against thickness x for African Balsam at (511keV)

Figure 3: a plot of attenuation coefficient against density

Each wood sample was classified into six categories labelled as A, B, C, D, E and F with each letter having the same thickness, area and volume for the five sampled woods as shown Table 1. Variations of attenuation coefficient with wood thickness at 1173-133KeV and 511KeV for the pair of African Balsam wood sample are presented in Figures 1- 2 from which it can be inferred that attenuation coefficient increases with wood thickness. These graphical results are similar for all the other wood samples and are in agreement with previous results of [1] who measured the attenuation coefficients for some woods in Kurnool district, India of thickness from about 5.0 cm and obtained the values of attenuation coefficient from about 0.0326 to 0.1050cm⁻¹ using Cobalt-60, Cesium-137 and Sodium-22 source and gamma spectrometer scintillation detector. However, the differences of less than 5% compared with the results are expected considering the fact that the equipment used and the radiation beam geometry were different from the present work. The results indicate that wood quality can be based on the gamma ray attenuation characteristics. The use of Cobalt-60 and Sodium-22 sources is to ascertain the validity of the results with different means and as shown in Figure 3, attenuation coefficient increases with wood thickness as well as wood density.

Conclusion

The results of this research have shown the dependence of wood attenuation coefficient on wood thickness, density and incident photon. In this finding, Mahogany with average density of 0.76g/cm³ has the highest attenuation coefficient while African Balsam with average density of 0.43g/cm³ has the lowest attenuation coefficient. These results among other things offer the usability of wood as radiation shielding material owing to the fact its radiation shielding capacity is easily estimated through its thickness, density and variation with incident photon.

References

- [1] Rajasekhav. E and Jeevan kumar. R, (2014). Experimental Investigation of Gamma Radiation Shielding Characteristics of wood. Molecular Biophysical Laboratory. *International Journal of Humanities, Arts Medicine and Sciences (BEST: IJHAMS)*. ISSN 2348-0521, Vol 2.
- [2] Chaudhari L. M. (2013). Study of Attenuation Coefficients of Leaves of Asoka Plant by using Cs and Tl sources. *Research Journal of Physical Sciences Vol.1(2),1-8*.
- [3] National Council on Radiation Protection and Measurements, (1976). Structure Shielding design and evaluation for medical use of X-rays and Gamma rays of energies up to 10MeV. Bethesda, MD: NCRP: NCRP Report No49.
- [4] Rajasekhar. E, Jeevan Kumar.R, Narasimham.K.L and Vankataramaniah.K; (2014). Comparism of Gamma ray Attenuation Coefficients of Wood materials with Theoretical Values. *Journal of Global Bioscience, Vol.4, PP.1836-1841*.
- [5] Ogunkunle, A.T. J; Ojo, O.D and Oni, O.M. (2014). Anatomy and Specific Gravity of wood sample from six Nigerian Tree Species in Relation to their Diagnosis X-ray Shielding Capabilities. *Journal of Natural Sciences Research, Nigeria. Vol. 4*.
- [6] Oni, O.M; Ogundare, A.T and AKinloye, M.K. (2001). Diagnostic X-ray Attenuation by some

Nigeria species of wood. *Nigeria Journal of Physics*. 13:46 -49.

- [7] Glass, Samuel V. and Zelinka, Samuel L. (2010). Moisture Relation and physical properties of wood. Wood as an engineering material: chapter 4. Centennial edition. General technical report FPL; GTR-190. Madison W.I: US. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Forest Productions Laboratory, p.4.1 – 4.19.
- [8] Chikkapa,U, (2013). Gamma ray Attenuation Study with varying Moisture Content of Clay Brick. *Internatinal Journal of Engineering Science Invention Vol.2, PP.35-38*.

Publisher's Note Scholar J remains neutral with regard to jurisdictional claims in published maps and institutional affiliations.